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SATISFACTION WITH PARENTAL LABOUR DIVISION

We assess the satisfaction with division of parental labour between partners in the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) data collected from 2020-2025

DATA ON OVER 30 000 RESPONDENTS AGED 18—49

In all of the observed regions, **men on average experience higher satisfaction with division of childcare than women.** Further analyses indicate that men take on a smaller share of childcare and typically focus on less burdensome tasks (for more details, please scan the QR code).

Across 16 countries and regions, the average satisfaction ranges from 8.0 to 9.1, indicating **high levels of satisfaction with the parental labour division.**

Specifically, men's satisfaction on childcare labour division ranges from approximately 7.8 in Hong Kong to about 9.5 in Moldova, while women's satisfaction varies between around 6.8 in Hong Kong and 8.9 in Moldova.

In most places, **the average satisfaction lies between 8 and 9,** however one could observe exceptions in Moldova and Uruguay (mean over 9), as well as Germany, Taiwan and Hong Kong (mean under 8).

MEAN SATISFACTION WITH THE DIVISION OF CHILDCARE

GGs OFFERS VALUABLE INSIGHTS INTO VARIOUS FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH PARENTAL LABOUR DIVISION.

Source: Generations and Gender Survey Round II – wave 1 (data from 2020-2025)

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The Generations and Gender Programme Preparatory Phase Project (GGP-5D)

